

Repurposing Waste Plastics into Cleaner Asphalt Pavement Materials and Its Environmental Performance Reusing Discarded Plastics to Create More Environmentally Friendly Asphalt Paving Ingredients and Its Environmental Performance

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Transportation infrastructure has remained a critical component of a country's economic and social growth. The need for new roads and upkeep of current roads is quite strong, particularly in emerging nations, as they are directly related to overall development. This is a plea for a paradigm shift in the way roads are constructed. Recent research have shed light on the need of greening and sustainable transportation, which can expedite the process of rescuing the world from additional severe situations. One of the most effective approaches to solve this issue is by the substitution or replacement of pavement layers with non-natural materials. Numerous studies have been conducted to determine the feasibility of employing different alternative materials in road building, especially recycled trash. The objective of this study is to assess the environmental implications of alternative materials such as waste plastics in road building and to demonstrate their viability. This is accomplished by evaluating several environmental effect criteria such as global warming potential, carbon footprint, and cost. The comparison of these materials demonstrates their use in pavement construction and their distinct limitations when used on a wide scale. This will result in more efficient, inexpensive, and sustainable pavement design and construction. Current practice of recycled waste plastics includes 7 major types: polyethylene terephthalate (PETE), high-density polyethylene (HDPE), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), low-density polyethylene (LDPE), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), and others such as acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA), polycarbonate (PC), and polyurethane (PU).

Keywords: PLASTIC, PAVEMENT, MATERIALS

Introduction

With 7 billion people on the globe and another billion on the way, humanity and other living things are suffering

from a man-made calamity known as global warming: the urgency of taking decisive action has never been greater or will be in the next century. Mother Nature's health and riches are contingent upon these moments when humans must alter their course and manner of life.

Sustainable development is development that satisfies current demands without jeopardizing future generations' ability to satisfy their own.

The world is running out of natural resources, and their over exploitation has resulted in a man-made calamity known as global warming and climate change. Excessive use of fossil fuels and natural resources has put the earth under extreme stress. This is why sustainable development methods are at the top of our priority list. The term "sustainable development" refers to a broad idea that covers several elements such as biodiversity conservation, social sustainability, and climate change mitigation. Our constructed environment is a significant contribution to this problem. This is where we spend the most resources and fossil fuels, resulting in increased carbon emissions and a larger carbon footprint. The built environment is made up of all the structures that sustain human civilisation, including buildings, roads, bridges, and all other man-made things.

While progress has been made in many industries toward integrating sustainability into our everyday lives, there is still a long way to go before attaining all aspects. These considerations apply to our Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which have been renamed Millennium Development Goals. These objectives are geared on preserving the health, prosperity, economy, and living circumstances of every person on the earth. This research will seek to address one of the development goals by examining one of the built environment's components: transportation infrastructure.

Transportation infrastructure has remained a critical component of a country's economic and social growth. It has an effect on commerce, production and consumption, as well as on health and other aspects. It is also a critical component of the employment market. Land, air, and sea modes of transportation exist, with the majority being roads and the other two being reliant on them. In this era of conflict about global warming and climate change, we are battling to modify our lifestyles in order to achieve sustainability. Road planning, design, construction, and maintenance have been in their infancy in terms of sustainability, whilst efforts are being made to develop and produce more sustainable buildings and goods. The road network's construction consumes enormous quantities of energy and the materials utilized are very unsustainable in nature. As with any civil building, its constituents, such as asphalt or bitumen in road construction, are generated by fractional distillation, which requires the combustion of crude oil, which the world is attempting to eliminate.

This sector generates the most greenhouse gases, both directly via the use of fossil fuels in mining, transportation, and paving, and indirectly through car emissions. Indeed, the continual growth of road cars and hence of traffic results in a significant increase in pollution and noise problems. -2015 World Highways

Transportation networks contribute to pollution and habitat fragmentation.

Additionally, the road construction sector faces enormous challenges, including cost reduction and improved production, construction, and, of course, maintenance, all the more so as raw materials become scarce and environmental regulations regarding air pollution and noise disturbances become stricter. As with the rest of

the industries, the road building industry must address the issue of sustainability.

This necessitates a paradigm shift in the way roads are constructed. Recent research have shed light on the need of greening and sustainable transportation, which can expedite the process of rescuing the world from additional severe situations. The good news is that several countries have taken measures, but they have not been implemented well. The need for new roads and upkeep of current roads is quite strong, particularly in emerging nations, as they are directly related to overall development.

As a result, we will examine and develop approaches and strategies for designing and constructing sustainable road infrastructures. Let us take a step further and examine the process's alternatives and the elements that contribute to the change of our typical routines.

Pavements and its types

Flexible pavement can be defined as the type of pavement which consists of a mixture of asphalt or bituminous material, aggregates (coarse and fine) placed on a bed of compacted granular material of appropriate quality in layers over the subgrade. The course aggregates can be crushed stone and fine aggregates are generally sand. (Both engineered to required specification). The Bitumen is the derived from tar which is the final product of fractional distillation of natural oil. These pavements generally designed for low volume traffic loads as compared to rigid pavements. The stress distribution in these pavements is such that it gradually recedes as the load is transmitted downwards from the surface by virtue of spreading over an increasingly larger area, by carrying it deep enough into the ground through successive layers.

Figure 1-Road section of a flexible pavement, 2011, Online manuals -Texas Department of Transportation

Figure 2- Road section of a rigid pavement, 2011 Online manuals -Texas Department of Transportation

Sustainability concepts and material considerations

"Climate change, as a single trend, influences all other trends." (Barack Obama, 2015 Paris Climate Conference). In 2015, the US federal highway administration published a study outlining the necessity for sustainability in the road industry. The two major aims of any road are to satisfy the technical criteria established for a long length of time on a specific site and to utilize ecologically safe materials and techniques to protect the ecosystem.

Sustainability is a continual endeavor in which established methods are modified and enhanced to match current objectives. This includes addressing concerns such as greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, energy consumption, habitat degradation, water quality, hydrologic cycle changes, air quality, transportation, access, freight, and community development, as well as the depletion of non-renewable resources and economic development. The primary motivator for adopting sustainable practices has been economics. Along with the pressing need to combat climate change and global warming, economics has shown to be a long-term asset for any firm that chooses to venture into this area of the industry. (2016 Global Green Building Trends). The materials used to construct the road are primarily taken from the surrounding area and modified to suit the required engineering specifications. These are critical components for road sustainability. Consider the following factors while planning roadways. These include lifecycle analysis and carbon footprint calculations.

The term "life cycle analysis" refers to a methodical examination of a product's whole life cycle, from raw materials through final disposal. It takes a cradle-to-grave perspective to a product or process, taking into account environmental considerations and potential consequences. (Williams's2009) It is one of the most effective ways for determining the amount of energy consumed throughout the course of a product's life. The carbon footprint is the total quantity of greenhouse gases created to sustain human activities directly and indirectly, typically represented in equivalent tons of carbon dioxide (CO₂) during a certain time period. (2016, timeforchange) This refers to the use of fossil fuels from the point of extraction to the location of the product at any given time. To achieve the sustainability goals for road infrastructure, it is critical to prioritize the usage of alternative materials and recycled components.

Industrial waste as virgin material

The bulk of issues encountered during road building and restoration are related to materials. The existing material system must be altered and new technologies implemented to make our roadways more environmentally friendly and safer. Alternative materials have been found and tested to be useful for making roadways more resistant to the elements. These alternative materials are essentially industrial waste that is hazardous to the environment but has the potential to perform similarly to virgin materials in other sectors.

Fig. 3: Recycling rate of municipal wastes, 2015, Wall Street Journal

ASH

Common industrial wastes such as ash (Fly Ash, Bottom Ash, Pond Ash, Magnetherm Slag) are increasingly being utilized in road and building construction.

When coal is burned in a power plant's furnace, approximately 80% of ash is produced. This component is transported in the flue gases and is collected using an electrostatic or cyclone precipitator. It is referred to as fly ash. The leftover ash sinters and settles to the bottom of the furnace, where it is referred to as bottom ash. Fly ash can be disposed of dry or in a pond as a water slurry. Pond ash is created when fly ash and bottom ash are combined and disposed of in ash ponds as a water slurry. Fly ash may degrade the ecosystem, posing health risks, and necessitating the use of huge amounts of landfill. Several countries, including India, have already established standards for the use of ash in road construction. It can be used to minimize settling in lightweight embankments. Additionally, ferry bumpers, composting, and safety barriers have been employed to reinforce and improve the drainage properties of the pavement. (2001, IRC SP-58).

Plastic

Polyethylene is a kind of polymer that has been researched for its potential to improve the characteristics of asphalt mixtures. To cover the aggregate, two kinds of polyethylene were used: high-density polyethylene (HDPE) and low-density polyethylene (LDPE) (LDPE). The findings suggest that ground HDPE polyethylene

modifiers have superior engineering characteristics. The modifier should be added at a rate of 12% by weight of bitumen. It was discovered that it increased stability, decreased density, and marginally increased air spaces and mineral aggregate voids. (2007) ([Mohammad](#))

Researchers estimate that 192 coastal nations discharged eight million tons of plastic into the seas in 2010. While this may appear to be an absurdly large sum, the quantity would be several times that. Apart from determining the overall amount, a recent research published in the journal *Science* identified the top 20 nations responsible for the most plastic garbage poured into the seas. India is one of the lowest performers in the world, ranking twelfth. It has discharged up to 0.24 million tons of plastic into the ocean each year and 0.6 million tons of unmanaged plastic trash. (Source: [The Hindu, 2015](#)). This is a paper highlighting the critical need to find solutions to the problem of hazardous waste contaminating water, land, and air at an exponential rate. One of the most effective solutions is to recycle these waste plastics for a variety of applications, such as road building. This necessitates an examination of the possibility of using this type of trash into road building. Additionally, recycled plastics have been proven to be suitable for use in the building of bituminous or asphalt roadways. The polymer used in plastics and the bitumen combination are resistant to high temperatures and water action. Due to the soundproofing qualities of plastics, noise pollution on roadways is reduced, and no harmful fumes are created. (2012) ([Swami](#)). This has been applied in practice on the highways of Himachal Pradesh, India, and has shown to be quite effective ([DNA India, 2010](#)). However, there are several phases involved in the process, from the collecting of waste plastics through their eventual use in building. Recycling plastics and preparing them for use in mix designs is critical. This is due to a number of economic and technological restrictions, such as the necessity for chemical modification in order to recover the components of the base chemical. ([1995, Rebeiz](#)). Appropriate rules and oversight are required. Numerous characteristics of bitumen make it inappropriate for pavements and might create traffic congestion. To begin, bitumen is a byproduct of the combustion of fossil fuels, which is a disaster for the environment. At elevated temperatures, road bleeding occurs, decreasing the performance of surface courses. Bitumen may fracture as a result of chemical processes such as oxidation. Bitumen separates from the aggregate, producing potholes on roads, due to the fact that it is a water resistant substance that degrades the life of roads when exposed to water. Due to the chemical makeup of plastic, it works as an excellent binder for bitumen. It softens at around 260 degrees Fahrenheit and produces no effervesces of any gasses between 260 and 350 degrees Fahrenheit. Possess a binding feature to facilitate the incorporation of these wastes into the building process.

Table 1-Results of SDBC Mix for Varying Percentages of LDPE (Rokade,2012)

SI No	LDPE (%)	BITUMEN (%)	MARSHAL STABILITY (Kg)	FLOW VALUE (mm)	BULK DENSITY (GM/CC)	AIR VOIDS% Vv	VOIDS IN MINERAL AGGREGATE(VMA)	% VOIDS FILLED WITH BITUMEN (VFB)
1	3	5	1050	3.10	2.24	3.86	15.04	74.12
2	6	5	1120	3.88	2.25	3.43	14.66	76.23
3	9	5	1185	3.91	2.25	3.21	14.48	77.18

Figure 4- Flow chart of a plastic waste management process,(Rebeiz, 1995)

Cost analysis

In the case of plastics, it can be used in two processes which are dry and wet processes. According to the study in CET(2012), it is possible to use around 15% of recycled plastic in a dry process and 8% in the wet process without any changes of the strength and performance of the bitumen.

Taking 1 mile of two-lane roadway, the amount of bitumen used is approximately 150 MetricTons. 15% of this amount =22.5 Metric Tons of recycled plastics =49604 lbs(1 MT=1000kg, 1kg=2.2lbs). The total amount of

recycled plastics can be purchased in the state of Florida for around \$0.3 per pound which equated to \$14,881 or the equivalent of \$15,000. By traditional means, the 22.5 Metric tons of pure bitumen costs approximately \$3 per gallon which results in a total amount of \$19,677.312. It proves that it is economically viable to use recycled plastics over pure nonrenewable fossil fuels.

Price

Figure 5- Energy Savings per Short Ton of Recycled Material compared to landfilling, (WARM-13)

Current difficulties in adopting the use of plastics materials in the design and construction of pavements

Traditional materials are abundant and readily available in the neighborhood of any building location.

The issue of updating substitute materials is not being raised on a local and regional level, despite the fact that the supply of these conventional materials would dwindle over time as their prices rise.

Alternative materials, such as recovered industrial waste, are not readily available, complicating the use. The governing authorities do not support the imposition of strict rules and regulations to promote sustainability.

There are no mandatory rules for all projects to use a green grading system (new construction, operation, maintenance and renovation). There is a dearth of research and development in the area of innovation and experimenting with alternative materials for demonstrating improved pavement performance. There is a dearth of information on the engineering and strength properties of recycled industrial wastes used in pavement applications. There is a dearth of data on the viability of implementing each and every alternate source of energy in each nation. Under development are more efficient and environmentally friendly off-site (ex-Ready mix plants) and on-site construction gear (ex-rollers and excavators).

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